

README

Post-link Outlining For Code Size Reduction

Introduction

This artifact is associated with the paper titled "**Post-link Outlining for Code Size Reduction**", which presents a novel approach to reducing the size of compiled binaries through a post-link optimization technique. Code size reduction is critical for resource-constrained environments, such as embedded systems and IoT devices, where memory and storage are limited.

Our method leverages post-link outlining to identify and extract repeated instruction sequences across the entire binary, creating reusable functions that replace the original sequences. This process occurs after the linking stage, enabling whole-program analysis and ensuring compatibility with various compiler front-ends and intermediate optimizations.

The input to our approach is a binary executable file, and the output is the optimized binary executable file with reduced code size. This artifact provides the implementation of our approach, along with all necessary scripts and instructions to reproduce the results presented in the paper. Users can analyze the impact of post-link outlining on code size reduction for their own binaries or the included benchmark set.

Artifact Requirements

1. Operating System and Architecture

- **Operating System:** Ubuntu 22.04
- **Architecture:** AArch64
- The artifact has not been validated on other operating systems or architectures. For smooth operation, it is recommended to use the same configuration as specified.

2. Hardware Requirements

- **Memory:** At least 8GB RAM
- **Storage:** At least 64GB of available hard disk space
- **CPU:** AArch64 architecture with a recommended clock speed of 2.2GHz or higher

3. Environment and Tools

- **Linux Environment**
- **make** command available (ensure `make` is installed)
- **perf** tool installed with the necessary permissions to run (e.g., `sudo` or sufficient privilege level)
- **Python** environment with the following libraries:
 - `os`
 - `re`
 - `subprocess`
 - `argparse`

- `openpyxl` (including `workbook` and `load_workbook`)

Usage Guide

1. Extract the Artifact Package:

First, unzip the `artifact_PLOS.tar` package. Run the following command to extract it:

```
tar -xzvf artifact_PLOS.tar
```

This will create the `artifact_PLOS` folder. After extraction, navigate into the `artifact_PLOS` directory:

```
cd artifact_PLOS
```

2. Set up Environment Variables:

Execute the `env.sh` script to set the necessary environment variables:

```
source env.sh
```

3. Navigate to `artifactFormibench`:

Move into the `artifactFormibench` directory:

```
cd artifactFormibench
```

4. Run the `run_makefiles.py` Script:

Execute the following command to start the process:

```
python run_makefiles.py
```

After completing the above steps, you will have obtained all the required data.

Results Explanation

After the script completes execution, five Excel files will be generated, named `figure5sdata.xlsx`, `figure6sdata.xlsx`, `figure7sdata.xlsx`, `figure8sdata.xlsx`, and `figure9sdata.xlsx`. The content of each file corresponds to the raw data for the figures in the paper. For example:

- `figure5sdata.xlsx` contains the raw data for **Figure 5** in the paper.
- `figure6sdata.xlsx` contains the raw data for **Figure 6** in the paper.
- Similarly, up to `figure9sdata.xlsx`.

By comparing the data, we believe that the information in these tables can effectively validate the experimental results presented in the paper.

Script Execution Flow

file Structure

- The project has the following directory structure:
 - `llvm-project/`: Contains the LLVM toolchain required for the artifact. This directory includes the necessary LLVM libraries and tools that the artifact depends on for compiling, optimizing, and generating code.
 - `gcc/`: Contains the GNU toolchain required for the artifact.
 - `env.sh`: This is the environment configuration script. It sets up the necessary environment variables, paths, and other configurations to ensure that the artifact can be built and executed properly.
 - `artifactFormibench/`: This directory contains the benchmark and testing scripts. It includes a variety of scripts designed to test the artifact's functionality, performance, and correctness under different conditions.

Toolchain Versions

The artifact relies on specific versions of Clang and GCC for building and compiling code:

- **Clang version:** 18.0.0
This version of Clang is used for the LLVM-based toolchain, ensuring compatibility with the LLVM optimizations and features required for the artifact.
- **GCC version:** 15.0.0
This version of GCC is used for the GNU toolchain, providing the necessary compiler and linker for the artifact's build process.

Additional Notes

1. False positive errors in correctness checks that may occur in Lout examples.

- **Cause:** The inconsistency is due to Lout including a step that prints the current time as part of its output. Since the time is generated dynamically, it may differ between runs, causing a mismatch in the output.
- **Solution:** You can manually use the `diff` command to compare the outputs, ignoring the time-related sections, and verify the correctness of the program by focusing on the functional and data consistency.

```
Ⓢ yuanshaobai@arm64:~/bolt/artifactFormibench/typeset$ diff output_large.ps bolt-output_large.ps
3c3
< %%CreationDate: Fri Jan 17 17:39:51 2025
---
> %%CreationDate: Fri Jan 17 17:43:50 2025
```

2. Missing Data Issue

- **Cause:** Some data may be missing because the `outline` optimization in the Clang compiler can introduce errors in the test results.
- **Solution:** The missing data is invalid and should be excluded from the analysis. Avoid using the affected tests for any critical performance or correctness evaluations.